

LIQUID RENEWABLE ENERGY CARRIERS FROM
CAPTURED CARBON EMISSIONS

DELIVERABLE D2.3

Evaluation Methodology

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The CAPTUS project addresses the challenge of reducing carbon emissions and maintaining competitiveness in energy-intensive industries by developing sustainable and cost-effective pathways for producing renewable energy carriers from industrial carbon emissions. The project demonstrates three distinct renewable energy carriers value chains at three different demonstration sites: a bioprocess for triglyceride production in a steel plant, microalgae cultivation for bio-oil production in a chemical plant, and electrochemical CO₂ reduction for formic acid production in a cement plant.

Deliverable 2.3, titled "Evaluation Methodology," aims at establishing a framework for assessing the technical, environmental, economic, and social performance of the project's demonstrators through tailored indicators. Those indicators are distinguished between Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and supplemental indicators. KPIs are emphasized as core metrics for tracking progress, while supplemental indicators provide additional, albeit less critical, insights. The indicators are designed to measure and monitor the performance of each demonstration site independently, without facilitating direct comparisons between sites.

The selected KPIs and supplemental indicators were developed through a four-step methodology that involved document analysis, the creation of tailored templates for each demonstration site, the completion of those templates through a collaborative process with project partners, and finally the validation of indicators and preparation of the evaluation methodology. For each indicator, a table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target, and Source of inspiration.

A total of 40 KPIs as well as of 45 supplemental indicators were identified across the three demonstration sites, categorized as follows:

- Demonstrator D1 (Steel Plant): 14 KPIs (7 technical, 3 environmental, 2 economic, 2 social) and 13 supplemental indicators.
- Demonstrator D2 (Chemical Plant): 14 KPIs (6 technical, 3 environmental, 3 economic, 2 social) and 17 supplemental indicators.
- Demonstrator D3 (Cement Plant): 12 KPIs (4 technical, 2 environmental, 3 economic, 3 social) and 15 supplemental indicators.

The evaluation of those indicators will be coordinated by different project teams, each responsible for specific categories of indicators, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the CAPTUS innovations. In particular, the responsibility for coordinating the collection and reporting of technical KPIs is assigned to technical WP leaders (WP3, WP4, WP5) i.e. BEPP for D1, A4F for D2, UNICAN for D3. Moreover, DRAXIS was assigned with the responsibility of coordinating environmental, economic, and social KPIs. Reporting on KPI target achievement will be included in the project's upcoming periodic reports No. 2 and No. 3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48].

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No deviations.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CSA	Continuous Swing Adsorption
D	Deliverable
DSP	Downstream processing
EC	European Commission
EIIs	Energy-Intensive Industries
ERCO₂	CO ₂ electrocatalytic reduction
HTL	Hydrothermal Liquefaction
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PHBs	Photobioreactors
PSA	Pressure Swing Adsorption
RECs	Renewable Energy Carriers
TAGs	Triacylglycerols
WP	Work package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

With ambitious climate policies in place, energy-intensive industries (EIs) are facing the challenge of maintaining competitiveness in global markets while significantly reducing carbon emissions. The CAPTUS project addresses this challenge by exploring sustainable and cost-effective pathways for producing high-value renewable energy carriers (RECs) from industrial carbon emissions, exploiting renewable electricity surplus. This approach aims to curtail the anthropogenic carbon cycle and meet both emission reduction targets and energy requirements.

In this context, the CAPTUS project demonstrates three complete REC value chains at different demonstration sites:

- DEMONSTRATOR D1: A bioprocess based on a two-stage fermentation to produce triglycerides in a steel plant.
- DEMONSTRATOR D2: Lipids-rich microalgae cultivation followed by hydrothermal liquefaction to produce bio-oils in a chemical plant.
- DEMONSTRATOR D3: Electrochemical reduction of CO₂ to produce formic acid in a cement plant.

Figure 1: CAPTUS Demonstrators Illustration [1]

Led by RINA-C, WP2, titled "Baseline assessment and definition of the project framework," focuses on establishing the foundational elements for developing CAPTUS solutions across the technical work packages (WP3, WP4, WP5).

Task 2.4, implemented from December 2023 to August 2024 (M7 to M15) and led by DRAXIS within WP2, aims to identify and compile *Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)* to evaluate the DEMOs' sustainability performance, covering environmental, economic, and social aspects. These KPIs are chosen based on innovation characteristics, demonstrators' site specifics, and other pertinent project considerations. The task also involves reviewing existing frameworks, particularly on carbon capture and utilization (CCU), to integrate relevant indicators. Key partners involved in Task 2.4 include BBEP, ARC, CIRCE, CISC, HCH, NOVIS, A4F, GCPV, SINTEF, UNICAN, and APRIA.

Deliverable 2.3, titled "Evaluation Methodology", includes the selection and definition of these KPIs along with guidelines for their proper measurement. The selected KPIs will be measured and monitored during project implementation to facilitate the assessment of the demonstrators' performance, enabling the quantification of the contribution of CAPTUS innovations to sustainability.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

Considering the above, the main objectives of this deliverable are:

- To identify and select a list of KPIs that reflect the performance of the CAPTUS solutions across environmental, economic, and social dimensions.
- The selected KPIs will also facilitate the assessment of the reference scenario (i.e., without the implementation of the CAPTUS solutions). This shall support and enable the quantification of the contribution of innovations to sustainability.
- To review existing European Commission Monitoring Frameworks and relevant literature to ensure the selected KPIs align with current state-of-the-art and up-to-date publications.
- To provide definitions and guidelines for the measurement of each KPI.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

To achieve its objectives, this deliverable is organised as follows:

Chapter 2: Description of demonstration sites describes an overall representation of the demonstration sites and provides specific details about each of the three demonstrators (D1, D2, and D3).

Chapter 3: Methodology explains the four-stage methodology used for the definition and selection of KPIs. The methodology includes the document analysis, the template-based selection of KPIs per demonstrator, the validation of KPIs with each DEMO partners, and finally, the finalisation of KPIs and the evaluation methodology.

Chapter 4: CAPTUS KPIs per demonstrator presents the selected KPIs for each of the three demonstrators (D1, D2, and D3). For each KPI, a table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target (success indicator), and Source of inspiration.

Chapter 5: CAPTUS supplemental indicators per demonstrator presents the selected supplemental indicators for each of the three demonstrators (D1, D2, and D3). A summary table for the supplemental indicator per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) is provided including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target (success indicator), and Source of inspiration.

Chapter 6: KPIs evaluation methodology outlines the approach and process to coordinate the collection of calculated KPIs and reports the progress toward setting the targets.

Chapter 7: Conclusion - Next Steps summarises the key findings and conclusions drawn from the work conducted in this task. It also provides recommendations for future work or implementation based on the results.

The *References* section provides a list of all sources cited throughout the report.

Annex I including the initial KPIs template (empty).

2 DESCRIPTION OF DEMONSTRATION SITES

Chapter 2 provides a brief overview of the demonstration sites and outlines the processes involved at each stage for the three demonstrators (D1, D2, and D3).

2.1 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 1 (D1)

LOCATION	ArcelorMittal, Ghent (Belgium)
EII	Steel
TECHNOLOGIES PER STAGE	Stage 1: Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) Stage 2: Gas fermentation Stage 3: Liquid fermentation, Strain engineering Stage 4: Downstream processing
PRODUCED RECS	Acetate and Triacylglycerols (TAGs)
KEY PARTICIPANTS	BBEPP, ARC, CSIC, CIRCE

CAPTUS demonstration site 1, situated at ArcelorMittal's steelmaking plant in Belgium (Figure 2), aims to demonstrate a complete CCU process by implementing a multi-stage fermentation technology to convert the captured CO₂ first into acetic acid (intermediate) and then into medium and long chain TAGs as final product.

Figure 2: ArcelorMittal's steelmaking plant © ArcelorMittal Belgium [1]

ArcelorMittal has already implemented an effective strategy to reduce carbon emissions by capturing and converting CO through gas fermentation to ethanol in the Steelanol project, where the side streams (PSA tail gas and fermenter off-gases) are currently used for energy production. CAPTUS will demonstrate the valorisation of these side streams in four stages, as shown below (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Illustration of processes at each stage of CAPTUS demonstration site D1 [1]

During **Stage 1** carbon-rich steel mill flue gases, produced by the operation of ARC industry, will be directed to the existing full-scale Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) installed at the company's site. This gas input will be separated in the PSA into two gas streams, rich in CO and CO₂, respectively. The former CO-rich PSA tail gas stream will be directed to the existing Steelanol facility to produce ethanol, while the CO₂-rich stream will be advanced to Stage 2 for anaerobic gas fermentation.

Stage 2 involves the conversion of CO₂/H₂ (present in the gas stream) into acetate via gas-substrate fermentation using *Moorella Thermoacetica*. Stage 2 will be initially tested in small-scale fermenters, before being scaled and demonstrated on-site in a mobile gas fermentation reactor. Optimization procedures are also foreseen in Stage 2, such as the optimization of the CO₂/H₂ ratio, and the valorisation of remaining CO for bacteria growth and acetate production.

In **Stage 3** a secondary bioconversion process to produce long-chain TAGs will be conducted using the aerobic yeast *Yarrowia lipolytica*. The yeast strains provided for Stage 3 of D1 are developed through strain engineering techniques employed by CSIC. At the project's initial stages, the direct conversion of acetate to TAGs will be optimized in lab-scale reactors by BBEPP. Stage 3 will conclude with a scaled-up demonstration of this novel two-stage fermentation process: aerobic fermentation of gas into acetate followed by anaerobic conversion of acetate into TAGs.

Finally, **Stage 4** involves the downstream processing (DSP) for TAGs isolation at BBEPP premises using techniques such as mechanical cell disruption, centrifugation, water removal, and dead-end filtration.

2.2 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 2 (D2)

LOCATION	HyChem industrial plant, Póvoa de Santa Iria (Portugal)
EII	Chemicals
TECHNOLOGIES	Stage 1: CO ₂ capture of variable & low-concentrated flows Stage 2: Rich-lipids microalgae cultivation in closed photobioreactors Stage 3: Hydrothermal Liquefaction (HTL) to high-energy content bio-oils
PRODUCED RECS	Bio-oils
KEY PARTICIPANTS	HCH, NOVIS, A4F, CIRCE

CAPTUS demonstration site 2 is located at HyChem's Industrial Site in Póvoa de Santa Iria (Portugal) (Figure 4), and it aims to develop and demonstrate a novel technology to convert CO₂ from chemical industry carbon emissions to assist the growth of microalgae and thus the subsequent production of lipid-rich bio-oils.

Figure 4: HyChem's Industrial Site in Póvoa de Santa Iria © HyChem [1]

The innovation provided by D2 relies not only on the avoidance of CO₂ emissions resulting from the operation of chemical plants in the atmosphere but also on the production of added-value, energy-dense bio-oils that can be used directly for combustion purposes or upgraded into *drop-in* fuels. CAPTUS project will demonstrate these processes in three stages, as presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Illustration of processes at each stage of CAPTUS demonstration site D2 [1]

During **Stage 1** a continuous cleaning of the input flue gas through columns will be employed and followed by N₂ and O₂ removal through special membranes, before the liquification of the purified CO₂ with a technology tested and provided by NOVIS.

The output CO₂-rich stream of Stage 1 will be used in the **Stage 2** of the demonstrator. In this stage, integrated solutions are deployed by A4F to direct the purified CO₂ into PBRs for microalgae cultivation. Specific optimization actions are also foreseen, as to allow the optimal CO₂ dissolution in the cultivation medium and its maximum consumption by the microalgae.

The overall CCU process will be completed in **Stage 3**, in which the cultivated microalgae are subject to a hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) process. Briefly, this final step dictates the extraction of macromolecules into bio-oil of high energy content. In the framework of the CAPTUS project, it is foreseen that the process will be optimized with a strong focus on production yields and production time.

2.3 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 3 (D3)

LOCATION	GCPV, Mataporquera (Spain)
EII	Cement
TECHNOLOGIES	Stage 1: Continuous Swing Adsorption (CSA) Stage 2: CO ₂ electrocatalytic reduction (ERCO ₂)
PRODUCED RECS	Formic acid / formate
KEY PARTICIPANTS	GCPV, SINTEF, UNICAN, APRIA, CIRCE

CAPTUS demonstration site 3 is located at the GCPV cement plant facilities in Mataporquera (Cantabria, Spain) (Figure 6), and it aims to produce formic acid/formate including carbon capture and utilization technologies, both coupled for an efficient and selective electrochemical conversion of CO₂ in continuous operation.

Figure 6: GCPV cement plant facilities in Mataporquera (Cantabria, Spain) © GCPV cement Plant [1]

On one hand, the innovative nature of this demonstrator lies in the significant reduction of CO₂ emissions typically associated with cement production. On the other hand, in the production of formic acid as a byproduct of the process. The latter product has promising characteristics for use as a liquid fuel or as a raw material to produce various chemicals and gasoline. CAPTUS project will demonstrate these processes in two stages, as presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Illustration of processes at each stage of CAPTUS demonstration site D3 [1]

In **Stage 1**, the flue gas stream generated by GCPV will be used as the input of the mobile continuous

swing adsorption reactor (CSAR) unit developed by SINTEF. In this unit, the CSAR absorption technology will be used to capture CO₂ and thus increasing the CO₂ concentration from what is in a flue gas.

In *Stage 2*, the enriched CO₂ steam will be utilized by applying ERCO₂ technology for producing formic acid/formate that has been successfully demonstrated in UNICAN labs. In the framework of the CAPTUS project, after optimization of the process, the upscale of the technology to pilot scale is foreseen. Specifically, the foreseen pilot will be built by APRIA and engineered to support the transformation of up to 60 kg/day of CO₂ into formic acid.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 OVERALL APPROACH

Indicators can be classified in many ways; however, the European Environment Agency (EEA) has developed a typology to clarify the distinct roles that indicators serve in decision-making processes. According to this typology, indicators can be categorized into two main types: (1) **descriptive or simple indicators**, which define a situation or trend and offer additional information, and (2) **performance indicators**, which measure phenomena and evaluate progress towards set targets. These performance indicators, which provide valuable information about the case in question, are commonly called **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** [2, 3]. KPIs and indicators sit at the top of an information pyramid, with primary and analysed data forming the foundation (Figure 8) [4].

Figure 8: Information Pyramid [2, 3, 4]

In general, KPIs are the core indicators that show progress toward a specific goal. KPIs provide a focus for strategic and operational improvement and help focus attention on what matters most [3]. As said, the main objective of CAPTUS Task 2.4 is to identify and select KPIs that reflect the performance of the CAPTUS solutions at three demonstration sites (D1, D2, D3) across environmental, economic, and social dimensions. To this end, we categorised our indicators into four distinct types:

- **Technical indicators:** These measure the operational performance and efficiency of the CAPTUS solutions.
- **Environmental indicators:** These assess the impact of CAPTUS solutions on the natural environment.
- **Economic indicators:** These evaluate the financial performance and economic benefits derived from the CAPTUS solutions.
- **Social indicators:** These measure the social impact of the CAPTUS solutions.

Furthermore, we distinguished between **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** and **supplemental indicators**. KPIs are emphasized as core metrics for tracking progress, while supplemental indicators provide additional, albeit less critical, insights. The KPIs are designed to measure and monitor the performance of each demonstration site independently, without facilitating direct comparisons between sites. This approach is based on the specific information provided by each DEMO-involved partner, ensuring that the results are context-specific and not intended for cross-site comparison. Additionally, the KPIs were determined and selected following the S.M.A.R.T. criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) as defined in Table 1.

Table 1: SMART KPIs – What is about? [4]

S	SPECIFIC	The KPIs should be clear and specific for each DEMO-involved partner. That means that everyone must be involved in their definition to know exactly what will be measured
M	MEASURABLE	The KPIs must be variables that can be tracked over time.
A	ATTAINABLE	The KPIs must be realistic and achievable. They will be used to measure specific objectives and the impact of the implemented technologies within each demo site.
R	RELEVANT	The KPIs defined must be relevant either for the project or the demo's involved partners. For that reason, the demo's targets and objectives should be considered as a starting point for their definition.
T	TIME-BOUND	The KPIs must have a defined period of time. Normally this period will be adapted to the project's lifetime. However, a longer or shorter period of time is open to be selected by each demo site as long as is properly justified.

The methodology that was applied was based on four steps as indicated in the following figure and are explained in the following sub-sections.

Figure 9: Methodological steps for KPIs development in the CAPTUS project

3.2 STEP 1: DOCUMENTS ANALYSIS

In alignment with the task description, Step 1 involved the review and analysis of important documents including:

- the Grant Agreement (Grant agreement ID: 101118265), focusing on the nature of the innovations, the demo-site-specific characteristics and needs, and work foreseen under the technical WPs (WP3, WP4, WP5);
- the nature of EII boundary conditions as defined in CAPTUS T2.1 and T2.2 and the related deliverable (D2.1);
- the results of other research and innovations projects on carbon capture and/or indicators development; and
- published scientific literature on the topic.

Regarding the 3 CAPTUS main innovation pillars (Figure 10), these focus on: I) the development and tuning of tailored CO₂ capture and conditioning technologies for EII sectors; II) the development and validation of innovative technologies for converting CO₂ into liquid energy carriers; and III) building of well-structured models for the design, integration and scaling-up of CCU technologies powered by renewable electricity [6].

Figure 10: Figure 2. CAPTUS main innovation pillars [6]

The main projects that were carefully studied are:

- FUELPHORIA (1 October 2023 - 30 September 2027): Accelerating the sustainable production of advanced biofuels and RFNBOs - from feedstock to end-use (Grant agreement ID: 101118286) [5].
- BioSFerA (1 April 2020 - 31 March 2024): BIOfuels production from Syngas FERmentation for Aviation and maritime use (Grant agreement ID: 884208) [7].
- CO2SMOS (1 May 2021 - 30 April 2025): Advanced chemicals production from biogenic CO₂ emissions for circular bio-based industries (Grant agreement ID: 101000790) [8].
- BRILIAN (1 June 2023 - 31 May 2027): Cooperative business models for bio-based chains in rural areas (Grant agreement ID: 101112436) [9].
- NENUPHAR (1 November 2023 - 30 April 2027): New governance models to enhance nutrient pollution handling and nutrients recycling (Grant agreement ID: 101082169) [10].

The main scientific publications that were reviewed are:

- Kapetaki Z., Miranda Barbosa E. (2019)., Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage Technology Development Report 2018 (CCUS) EUR 29909 EN. European Commission. Luxemburg. ISBN 978-92-76-12440-5. doi:10.2760/185420. JRC118297 [11].
- Andrea Ramirez Ramirez, Aïcha El Khamlichi, Georg Markowz, Nils Rettenmaier, Martin Baitz, Gerfried Jungmeier, and Tom Bradley. (2020). LCA4CCU Guidelines for Life Cycle Assessment of Carbon Capture and Utilisation [12].
- Naims, H. (2016). Economics of carbon dioxide capture and utilization—a supply and demand perspective. Environ Sci Pollut Res 23, 22226–22241 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-6810-2> [13].
- M. Pérez-Fortes and E. Tzimas. (2016). Techno-economic and environmental evaluation of

carbon dioxide utilisation for fuel production. Synthesis of methanol and formic acid.; EUR 27629 EN. doi: 10.2790/981669 [14].

- Rafiaani, P., Dikopoulou, Z., Van Dael, M. et al. (2020). Identifying Social Indicators for Sustainability Assessment of CCU Technologies: A Modified Multi-criteria Decision Making. Soc Indic Res 147, 15–44 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-019-02154-4> [15].

3.3 STEP 2: TEMPLATE-BASED SELECTION OF KPIS PER DEMO

Following the successful completion of Step 1, DRAXIS proceeded with Step 2. This step involved the development of a template in an Excel file (*ANNEX I*) and the preselection, by DRAXIS, of proposed indicators for each demonstrator (D1, D2, D3). Different indicators were proposed for each demonstration site to ensure relevance and specificity. For all demonstrators, the template included detailed information organized into the following columns:

- **Demonstrator number** (*Column A*): Indicating the Demonstrator number (e.g., D1, D2, D3).
- **Category of indicator** (*Column B*): Specifying the KPI category (i.e., Technical, Environmental, Economic, Social).
- **Indicator identifier** (*Column C*): Providing a unique identifier for each KPI, created using a specific naming scheme. The format used is DEMO_Type_Number, where:
 - DEMO: The demonstrator number (e.g., D2).
 - Type: A short abbreviation of the KPI category (e.g., TECH for Technical, ENV for Environmental, ECON for Economic, SOC for Social).
 - Number: A sequential number to uniquely identify each KPI within its category.
 - Example: D2_TECH_01.
 - For supplemental indicators, the letter S was included before the sequential number e.g. D1_ENV_S_01.
- **Indicator name** (*Column D*): Providing a short, descriptive name for the indicator that clearly conveys what is being measured.
- **Formula** (*Column E*): Detailing the calculation equation or formula used to determine the value of the indicator to ensure consistency in measurement.
- **Unit of Measurement** (*Column F*): Specifying the unit in which the KPI is measured (e.g., percentage, number of units, tons, etc.).
- **Description** (*Column G*): Offering a detailed yet concise description of the indicator, including what it measures and its relevance to the project.
- **Responsible partner** (*Column H*): Identifying the partner responsible for providing input and monitoring this KPI. Confirming if you are the appropriate partner, or specifying who should be responsible.
- **Timeframe** (and/or Frequency) (*Column I*): Indicating when and how often the indicator should be measured (e.g., monthly, quarterly, annually).
- **Means of Verification** (*Column J*): Describing the methods and data sources used to collect

and verify the data for this indicator.

- **Target (Column K):** Defining the specific target or goal for this indicator. This target should be realistic and achievable within the context of the project.
- **Source of Inspiration (Column L):** Including references to sources that inspired the formulation of this indicator, such as GA, R&I projects on CCUS and/or indicator development, publications, and reports.
- **Core or Supplemental indicator? (Column M):** Indicating by writing "Core", if the partner proposes this indicator as a critical and mandatory KPI to be measured/monitored, or "Supplemental" for indicators that are supplementary to KPIs and not mandatory to measure.

3.4 STEP 3: VALIDATION OF KPIS WITH EACH DEMO PARTNER

After implementing Step 2, the validation of KPIs took place through a structured process. Initially, three separate online calls were organized by DRAXIS for each demonstration site. During each online meeting, DRAXIS presented to the demo partners the aim of Task 2.4, the methodology, and the expected contribution from them to complete the task's objectives. Moreover, during these meetings, DRAXIS presented the pre-selected indicators specific to each demonstrator. The initial meetings aimed to gather first responses from the demo partners. In some cases, these meetings promoted collaborative efforts to create a mutual understanding of the indicators. Following the initial meetings, several internal discussions among the partners of each demonstrator were organized. These discussions facilitated deeper insights and consensus on the proposed indicators. Then, each demo partner provided feedback to DRAXIS. This feedback was used to consolidate the work and harmonize the approach across the different demonstration sites. Following this, DRAXIS organized a second round of validation online. Three separate meetings, one per demonstrator, were held to present the consolidated list of indicators and finalize the KPIs, distinguishing between KPIs and supplemental indicators.

3.5 Step 4: Finalisation of KPIs and of evaluation methodology

Finally, a third round of validation was conducted through email, allowing the DEMO partners to review the proposed KPIs and suggest any potential changes. After the finalisation of KPIs in the Excel file, the relevant information was included in the present deliverable. For each demonstrator and each KPI and supplemental indicator, a table was provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the information gathered in the abovementioned template (section 3.3). The methodology was concluded with the definition of the KPIs evaluation methodology which outlines the approach and process to coordinate the collection of calculated KPIs and report the progress toward the targets set in the CAPTUS project.

4 CAPTUS KPIS PER DEMONSTRATOR

4.1 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 1 (D1)

For D1, 14 KPIS were selected: 7 technical, 3 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social. For each KPI, a table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target, and Source of inspiration. The completed template is provided in Annex II

4.1.1 TECHNICAL KPIS

4.1.1.1 D1_TECH_01: CO₂ CAPTURED

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_01
Indicator name	CO ₂ captured
Formula	Mass of CO ₂ captured/ year
Unit	kg/y
Description	This indicator is related to Stage 2. It calculates the amount of CO ₂ captured (CO ₂ to Acetate) per year at the demo scale.
Responsible partner	BBEPP
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements to calculate the cumulative amount of CO ₂ captured on a yearly basis until the end of the project [M48].
Means of verification	Measurement of the mass of CO ₂ captured per year [Task 3.5]
Target (success indicator)	2.5 kg CO ₂ /day
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]

4.1.1.2 D1_TECH_02: ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF THE OVERALL PROCESS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_02
Indicator name	Energy efficiency of the overall process
Formula	Energy consumed (Demo) + Energy to make H ₂ / Mass of final oil
Unit	kWh/kg final oil
Description	Measures the total energy consumed during the production process, including the energy required to make hydrogen, expressed per kilogram of final oil product. This indicator helps assess the energy efficiency of the overall production process.
Responsible partner	BBEPP & ARC

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_02
Timeframe	- Monthly measurements starting from [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Energy consumption records, production logs, and process efficiency reports.
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later stage
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.1.1.3 D1_TECH_03: ACETATE PRODUCTIVITY

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_03
Indicator name	Acetate productivity
Formula	Concentration of acetic acid / Fermentation time
Unit	g/L/h
Description	This indicator is related to Stage 2. The rate at which acetate is produced per unit volume per hour.
Responsible partner	BBEPP
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	To measure acetate productivity, determination of the total acetate produced, recording of the fermentation broth volume, and noting of the fermentation duration are required. Calculation of productivity is done using these values in the provided formula [Task 3.5].
Target (success indicator)	0.7 g/L/h
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]

4.1.1.4 D1_TECH_04: ACETATE CONCENTRATION OF 1ST FERMENTATION STAGE

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_04
Indicator name	Acetate concentration of 1st fermentation stage
Formula	Direct measurement of concentration
Unit	g/L
Description	This indicator is related to Stage 2. Acetate concentration of the fermentation broth production during the demo campaign
Responsible partner	BBEPP
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_04
Means of verification	Measuring acetate concentration will be done using analytical chemistry methods [Task 3.5]
Target (success indicator)	25-30 g/L
Source of inspiration	- CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6] - FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.1.1.5 D1_TECH_05: TAGS PRODUCTIVITY

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_05
Indicator name	TAGs productivity
Formula	Amount of TAGs produced/ Volume of fermentation broth × Fermentation time
Unit	g/L/h
Description	This indicator is related to Stage 3. The rate at which TAGs are produced per unit volume per hour.
Responsible partner	BBEPP
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	To measure TAGs productivity, determination of the total TAGs produced, recording of the fermentation broth volume, and noting of the fermentation duration are required. Calculation of productivity is done using these values in the provided formula [T3.5].
Target (success indicator)	0.5-1.5 g/L/h
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]

4.1.1.6 D1_TECH_06: TAGS CONCENTRATION OF 2ND FERMENTATION STAGE

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_06
Indicator name	TAGs concentration of 2nd fermentation stage
Formula	Direct measurement of concentration
Unit	g/L
Description	This indicator is related to Stage 3. TAGs concentration of the fermentation broth production during the DEMO campaign
Responsible partner	BBEPP
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_06
Means of verification	Measuring TAGs concentration will be done using analytical chemistry methods [Task 3.5]
Target (success indicator)	50-100 g/L
Source of inspiration	- CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6] - FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.1.1.7 D1_TECH_07: TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_07
Indicator name	Technology Readiness Level
Formula	-
Unit	-
Description	Based on the innovations that will be developed, the DEMO 1 processes will advance from Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 4-5 to TRL 7 within the context of the CAPTUS project.
Responsible partner	BBEPP, CIRCE, CSIC, ARC
Timeframe	Estimation at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Estimation based on the technical progress of WP3 tasks
Target (success indicator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas Fermentation of BFG to Produce Acetate: TRL4-5: Gas fermentation of biogenic CO₂ and syngas to acetate is established at the pilot scale.--> TRL7: Implementing the process for new gaseous substrate (PSA tail gas from the steel industry), on-site integration, and scale-up. • Multi-Stage Fermentation Process of Steel Industrial Flue Gases to Produce TAGs TRL5: Decoupled fermentation of acetate to TAGs established at pilot scale by BBEPP.--> TRL7: Coupled, in-line fermentation of acetate (from CO₂ fermentation) to TAGs in a real industrial environment. Downstream purification was demonstrated using pilot equipment. • New Engineered Oleaginous Yeasts to Yield TAGs from Acetate: TRL4-5: <i>Y. lipolytica</i> strains capable of high yield lipid production using acetate as a carbon source. -> TRL7: Strain engineering to develop recombinant obese strains of <i>Y. lipolytica</i> to improve lipid production using acetate.
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (nature of the innovations) [6]

4.1.2 ENVIRONMENTAL KPIS

4.1.2.1 D1_ENV_01: PERCENTAGE CHANGE OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ENV_01
Indicator name	Percentage change in environmental impact
Formula	$100 * ((\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq before} - \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq after}) / \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq before})$
Unit	%
Description	This indicator measures the reduction in CO ₂ eq. emissions (measured in kilograms of CO ₂ equivalent, kg CO ₂ eq) as a result of implementing the DEMO solutions. The indicator is expressed as a percentage, reflecting the efficiency of these solutions in reducing CO ₂ emissions compared to a conventional scenario where these solutions were not applied.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 1 partners
Timeframe	- Estimation of CO ₂ eq from conventional routes [M35] - Estimation of CO ₂ eq from innovative routes [M35, M45]
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Kapetaki & Barbosa (2018) [11]

4.1.2.2 D1_ENV_02: GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL (GWP)

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ENV_02
Indicator name	Global Warming Potential (GWP)
Formula	GWP will be calculated based on separate indicators i.e. Climate Change Biogenic, Climate Change Fossil, Climate Change Land Use, and Land Use Change.
Unit	kg CO ₂ -equivalents (kg CO ₂ -eq) per functional unit (FU)
Description	Quantifies the contribution to global warming of a unit of greenhouse gas emitted, usually measured in CO ₂ -equivalents.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 1 partners
Timeframe	- Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Ramirez et al. (2020) [12]

4.1.2.3 D1_ENV_03: USE OF RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY SURPLUS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ENV_03
Indicator name	Use of renewable electricity surplus
Formula	% of the energy needed for CO ₂ capture (OR total energy needed for the CAPTUS demo) that comes from RE surplus
Unit	%
Description	Suggestion is a formula that specifies how much of the extra energy needed (either for CO ₂ capture or considering the global process) comes from RE surplus.
Responsible partner	BBEPP & ARC & CIRCE
Timeframe	- Monthly measurements starting from [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	[Task 3.5]
Target (success indicator)	10 kW (BBMPP unit)
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]

4.1.2.4 D1_ENV_04: USE OF RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY SURPLUS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ENV_04
Indicator name	Amount of renewable energy
Formula	Direct measurement of renewable energy consumption.
Unit	kWh
Description	Amount of renewable energy consumed during the DEMO campaign.
Responsible partner	BBEPP & ARC & CIRCE
Timeframe	- Monthly measurements starting from [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of the power consumption of the containerized fermentation plant [3.5]
Target (success indicator)	There isn't a real target for this indicator. It has to be tested in real conditions and measured. The measured value could be potentially used as base for project's TEA.
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA [6]

4.1.3 ECONOMIC KPIS

4.1.3.1 D1_ECON_01: LEVELISED COST OF TAGS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ECON_01
Indicator name	Levelised Cost of TAGs
Formula	$\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\text{CAPEX}_t + \text{OPEX}_t) \cdot \frac{1}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAPEX_t: Capital costs i.e. costs associated with the initial investment and capital expenditures in year t. • OPEX_t: Operating and Maintenance Costs i.e. ongoing costs required for operation and maintenance of the bio-oil production demonstrator in year t. • E_t: Amount of bio-oil produced i.e. quantity of bio-oil produced in year t. • r: Discount Rate i.e. the rate used to discount future costs and revenues to their present value. It reflects the time value of money. • n: Lifetime of the project i.e. the total duration (in years) over which the bio-oil production project is expected to operate.
Unit	€/TAGs kg
Description	The levelised Cost of Bio-oil is a measure used to compare the cost-effectiveness of bio-oil production methods over their entire lifecycle. It is calculated as the total cost of producing bio-oil, including capital, operating, and maintenance costs, divided by the total amount of bio-oil produced over the system's lifetime.
Responsible partner	UNIGE & DRAXIS (help from ARC & BBEPP)
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T3.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.1.3.2 D1_ECON_02: POTENTIAL RETURN ON INVESTMENT

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ECON_02
Indicator name	Potential Return on Investment (ROI) Net profit/total investment * 100%
Formula	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Net Profit: The total revenue generated by the investment minus the total costs (both capital and operational costs). • Total Investment: The total capital expenditure (CAPEX) invested in the project.
Unit	%

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ECON_02
Description	ROI is a measure of profitability expressed as a percentage, indicating how effectively the investment is generating profit relative to its cost.
Responsible partner	UNIGE & DRAXIS (help from ARC & BBEPP)
Timeframe	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T3.5]
Means of verification	To be calculated in the previously mentioned Tasks
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.1.4 SOCIAL KPIs

4.1.4.1 D1_SOC_01: JOBS CREATION

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_SOC_01
Indicator name	Direct/indirect job creation due to project implementation
Formula	Number of new jobs/years
Unit	Number/y
Description	This indicator measures the total number of jobs created as a direct or indirect result of the implementation of the CAPTUS project.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 1 partners
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	4
Source of inspiration	- CAPTUS GA [6] - BioSFerA project [7] - FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.1.4.2 D1_SOC_02: EMPLOYEES' SKILLS AND TRAINING

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_SOC_02
Indicator name	Employees' skills and training in innovative processing
Formula	Number of training hours dedicated to innovative processing/year
Unit	h/y
Description	This indicator measures the total number of training hours allocated specifically to enhancing skills in innovative processing techniques that will be developed in the project annually.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 1 partners

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_SOC_02
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of WP3 - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	BioSFerA project [7]

4.2 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 2 (D2)

For D2, 14 KPIs were selected: 6 technical, 3 environmental, 3 economic, and 2 social. For each KPI, a table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target, and Source of inspiration. The completed template is provided in Annex III.

4.2.1 TECHNICAL KPIs

4.2.1.1 D2_TECH_01: CO₂ CAPTURED

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_01
Indicator name	CO ₂ captured
Formula	Mass of CO ₂ captured/ year
Unit	kg/y
Description	It calculates the amount of CO ₂ captured per year at the demo scale.
Responsible partner	NOVIS supported by HCH
Timeframe	Monthly measurements to calculate the cumulative amount of CO ₂ captured for each year.
Means of verification	Measurement of the mass of CO ₂ captured per year [Task 4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined (Based on GA 500 kg/y was the target, but this value might be revised according to the final PBR and HTL designs and scale)
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]

4.2.1.2 D2_TECH_02: ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF OVERALL PROCESS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_02
Indicator name	Energy efficiency of the overall process
Formula	Energy consumed (Demo) / Mass of final oil
Unit	kWh/kg final oil
Description	Measures the total energy consumed during the production process expressed per kilogram of final oil product. This indicator helps assess the energy efficiency of the overall production process.
Responsible partner	A4F supported by CIRCE, NOVIS, HCH
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Energy consumption records, and mass production of oil [Task 4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later stage
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.2.1.3 D2_TECH_03: ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF CO₂ CAPTURE

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_03
Indicator name	Energy efficiency of CO ₂ capture
Formula	Total energy consumption/amount of CO ₂ captured
Unit	kWh/kg of CO ₂ captured
Description	Energy Efficiency of CO ₂ Capture measures the energy required to capture and purify one kilogram of CO ₂ from low-concentrated and variable flue gases.
Responsible partner	HCH supported by NOVIS
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of kWh required to capture and purify, and mass of CO ₂ captured [T4.5]
Target (success indicator)	- Based on GA: 0.5 kWh per kg of liquefied CO ₂ , which constitutes a decrease of the energy demand of ca. 30% compared to commercially available CARBFIX solutions (HCH) -1 kWh/kg (proposed by NOVIS)
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]

4.2.1.4 D2_TECH_04: BIO-OIL MASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY FROM CO₂

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_04
Indicator name	Bio-oil mass conversion efficiency from CO ₂
Formula	Mass of bio-oil produced/mass of CO ₂ captured x 100%
Unit	%
Description	Conversion ratio of kg CO ₂ captured to the kg of final biooil produced.
Responsible partner	CIRCE supported by NOVIS, HCH, A4F
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of the mass of bio-oil and of CO ₂ captured to be utilised for this production [T4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	- FUELPHORIA project [5] - BioSFerA project [7]

4.2.1.5 D2_TECH_05: BIO-OIL ENERGY CONVERSION EFFICIENCY FROM CO₂

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_05
Indicator name	Bio-oil mass energy efficiency from CO ₂
Formula	Energy produced per kg of bio-oil / total energy needed to produce this kg of bio-oil x 100%
Unit	%
Description	Aims to answer: how much energy is needed to produce the energy of a kg of bio-oil? Is this a positive conversion energy-wise, or way too energy intensive?
Responsible partner	CIRCE supported by NOVIS, HCH, A4F
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of the energy produced by bio-oils and of CO ₂ captured to be utilised for this production [Task 4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	-

4.2.1.6 D2_TECH_06: TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_06
Indicator name	Technology Readiness Level
Formula	-
Unit	-
Description	Based on the innovations that will be developed, the DEMO 2 processes will advance from Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 4-5 to TRL 7 within the context of the CAPTUS project.
Responsible partner	HCH, A4F, NOVIS, CIRCE
Timeframe	Estimation at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Estimation based on the technical progress of WP4 tasks
Target (success indicator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced PBRs design and operation procedure to produce rich-lipid microalgae: TRL4-5. Microalgae production using CO₂ from gaseous effluents demonstrated at pilot scale.--> TRL7. Demonstration of efficient rich-lipid microalgae production in real industry sites using bespoke PBRs configuration and operation modes. • Optimised HTL to convert rich-lipids microalgae into high-content bio-oils TRL4-5. Reaction conditions and catalysts are optimised at the lab level with several feedstocks. TRL7. Tailored-made HTL processing and upgrading treatments for rich-lipid microalgae • Numerical simulation of algae HTL in pilot plant scale stirred-tank reactor TRL4-5. CFD simulation of HTL reactors at lab-scale in different geometries --> TRL7. CFD simulations at a semi-industrial scale with validated against experimental data of microalgae <i>Tetraselmis sp</i> HTL.
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (nature of the innovations)

4.2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL KPIS

4.2.2.1 D2_ENV_01: PERCENTAGE CHANGE OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ENV_01
Indicator name	Percentage change in environmental impact
Formula	$100 * ((\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq before} - \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq after}) / \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq before})$
Unit	%
Description	This indicator measures the reduction in CO ₂ eq. emissions (measured in kilograms of CO ₂ equivalent, kg CO ₂ eq) as a result of implementing the DEMO solutions. The indicator is expressed as a percentage, reflecting the efficiency of these solutions in reducing CO ₂ emissions compared to a conventional scenario where these solutions were not applied.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners
Timeframe	- Estimation of CO ₂ eq from conventional routes [M35] - Estimation of CO ₂ eq from innovative routes [M35, M45]
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Kapetaki & Barbosa (2018) [11]

4.2.2.2 D2_ENV_02: GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL (GWP)

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ENV_02
Indicator name	Global Warming Potential (GWP)
Formula	GWP will be calculated based on separate indicators i.e. Climate Change Biogenic, Climate Change Fossil, Climate Change Land Use, and Land Use Change.
Unit	kg CO ₂ -equivalents (kg CO ₂ -eq) per functional unit (FU)
Description	Quantifies the contribution to global warming of a unit of greenhouse gas emitted, usually measured in CO ₂ -equivalents.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners
Timeframe	- Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Ramirez et al. (2020) [12]

4.2.2.3 D2_ENV_03: USE OF RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY SURPLUS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ENV_03
Indicator name	Amount of renewable energy
Formula	Direct measurement of renewable energy consumption.
Unit	kWh
Description	Amount of renewable energy consumed during the DEMO campaign.
Responsible partner	HCH supported from all partners
Timeframe	- Monthly measurements starting from [M32] - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of the power consumption of the containerized fermentation plant [Task 3.5]
Target (success indicator)	~100%
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA [6]

4.2.3 ECONOMIC KPIS

4.2.3.1 D2_ECON_01: LEVELISED COST OF BIO-OIL

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ECON_01
Indicator name	Levelised Cost of bio-oil
Formula	$\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\text{CAPEX}_t + \text{OPEX}_t) \cdot \frac{1}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAPEX_t: Capital costs i.e. costs associated with the initial investment and capital expenditures in year t. • OPEX_t: Operating and maintenance Costs i.e. ongoing costs required for operation and maintenance of the bio-oil production demonstrator in year t. • E_t: Amount of bio-oil produced i.e. quantity of bio-oil produced in year t. • r: Discount Rate i.e. the rate used to discount future costs and revenues to their present value. It reflects the time value of money. • n: Lifetime of the project i.e. the total duration (in years) over which the bio-oil production project is expected to operate.
Unit	€/ kg bio-oils
Description	The levelised Cost of Bio-oil is a measure used to compare the cost-effectiveness of bio-oil production methods over their entire lifecycle. It is calculated as the total cost of producing bio-oil, including capital, operating, and maintenance costs, divided by the total amount of bio-oil produced over the system's lifetime.
Responsible partner	UNIGE & DRAXIS with contribution from pilot partners
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ECON_01
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.2.3.2 D2_ECON_02: LEVELISED COST OF CO₂ CAPTURE

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ECON_02
Indicator name	Levelised Cost of CO ₂ Capture

$$\frac{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{CAPEX_{CO_2,t} + OPEX_{CO_2,t}}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{M_t}{(1+r)^t}}$$

Formula

- CAPEX CO_{2,t}: Capital costs specifically for CO₂ capture in year t.
- OPEX CO_{2,t}: Operating and maintenance costs specifically for CO₂ capture in year t.
- M_t: Mass of CO₂ captured in year t.
- r: Discount Rate i.e. the rate used to discount future costs and revenues to their present value. It reflects the time value of money.
- n: Lifetime of the project i.e. the total duration (in years) over which the bio-oil production project is expected to operate.

Unit	€/ kg CO ₂ captured
Description	The levelised Cost of CO ₂ Capture is an economic indicator used to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of CO ₂ capture technologies. It is calculated by dividing the total cost of capturing CO ₂ (including capital, operational, and maintenance costs) by the total amount of CO ₂ captured over the system's lifetime.
Responsible partner	UNIGE & DRAXIS with contribution from pilot partners
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.2.3.3 D2_ECON_03: POTENTIAL RETURN ON INVESTMENT

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_ECON_03
Indicator name	Potential Return on Investment (ROI)
	Net profit/total investment * 100%
Formula	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Net Profit: The total revenue generated by the investment minus the total costs (both capital and operational costs). • Total Investment: The total capital expenditure (CAPEX) invested in the project.
Unit	%
Description	ROI is a measure of profitability expressed as a percentage, indicating how effectively the investment is generating profit relative to its cost.
Responsible partner	UNIGE & DRAXIS with contribution from pilot partners
Timeframe	- Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	Techno-economic task [T6.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.2.4 SOCIAL KPIS

4.2.4.1 D2_SOC_01: JOBS CREATION

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_SOC_01
Indicator name	Direct/indirect job creation due to project implementation
Formula	Number of new jobs/years
Unit	Number/y
Description	This indicator measures the total number of jobs created as a direct or indirect result of the implementation of CAPTUS project.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial measurement at the beginning of WP4 - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	4
Source of inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CAPTUS GA [6] - BioSFerA project [7] - FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.2.4.2 D2_SOC_02: EMPLOYEES' SKILLS AND TRAINING

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D2_SOC_02
Indicator name	Employees' skills and training in innovative processing
Formula	Number of training hours dedicated to innovative processing/year
Unit	h/y
Description	This indicator measures the total number of training hours allocated specifically to enhancing skills in innovative processing techniques that will be developed in the project annually.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of WP4 - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	BioSFerA project [7]

4.3 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 3 (D3)

For D3, 12 KPIs were selected: 4 technical, 2 environmental, 3 economic, and 3 social. For each KPI, a table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target, and Source of inspiration. The completed template is provided in Annex IV.

4.3.1 TECHNICAL KPIs

4.3.1.1 D3_TECH_01: CO₂ CAPTURED

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_TECH_01
Indicator name	CO ₂ capture ratio
Formula	CO ₂ captured (kg/day)/ CO ₂ otherwise emitted (kg/day)
Unit	%
Description	It measures the amount of CO ₂ captured as a proportion of the total CO ₂ that would have been emitted without CO ₂ capture.
Responsible partner	SINTEF & GCPV
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T5.5 [M32] - Continuous measurements during demonstration [M32-M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of the CO ₂ fraction in the flue gas after the CSAR reactor compared to the measured CO ₂ fraction in the GCPV flue gas, as well as a measurement of the flow rate in the adsorber [Task 5.5]
Target (success indicator)	90% The CSAR pilot was recently demonstrated to capture around 80% of CO ₂ from the flue gas from a waste-to-energy plant. Based on that

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_TECH_01
	demonstration, several upgrades to the CSAR pilot are planned, which are expected to improve the capture ratio to above 90%.
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.3.1.2 D3_TECH_02: ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF CO₂ CONVERSION

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_TECH_02
Indicator name	Energy efficiency of the conversion process
Formula	Energy consumed (CO ₂ conversion) / Mass of HCOOH
Unit	kWh/kg HCOOH
Description	Measures the total energy consumed during the production process expressed per kilogram of final HCOOH product. This indicator helps assess the energy efficiency of the overall production process.
Responsible partner	GCPV & APRIA
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T5.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements to calculate the cumulative amount of CO ₂ captured in a yearly basis until the end of the project [M48].
Means of verification	Energy consumption records of the CO ₂ electrolyser, and mass production of HCOOH [Task 5.5]
Target (success indicator)	Estimation from lab scale data ERCO ₂ : 5 kWh/kg HCOOH To be determined in the real pilot plant
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.3.1.3 D3_TECH_03: FORMIC ACID MASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY FROM CO₂

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_TECH_04
Indicator name	Formic acid mass conversion efficiency from CO ₂
Formula	[Mass of formic acid produced/mass of CO ₂ captured corrected with the stoichiometry of the reaction and the molecular weights of CO ₂ and formic acid] x 100%
Unit	%
Description	Conversion ratio of kg CO ₂ captured to the kg of final formic acid produced.
Responsible partner	GCPV & SINTEF & UNICAN
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T5.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements

	- Measurement at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurement of the mass of formic acid and of CO ₂ captured to be utilised for this production [Task 4.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	- BioSFerA

4.3.1.4 D3_TECH_04: TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_TECH_06
Indicator name	Technology Readiness Level
Formula	-
Unit	-
Description	Based on the innovations that will be developed, the DEMO 2 processes will advance from Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 4-5 to TRL 7 within the context of the CAPTUS project.
Responsible partner	GCPV, SINTEF, UNICAN, APRIA
Timeframe	Estimation at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Estimation based on the technical progress of WP5 tasks
Target (success indicator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSAR based swing adsorption CO₂ capture TRL5. Swing adsorption reactor demonstrated at a pre-pilot scale --> TRL7. Demonstration and validation under real flue gas from cement plant and integration with ERCO2 stage • Optimised techniques for manufacturing GDEs TRL4-5. Feasibility of spray pyrolysis proven by manufacturing GDE of 10 cm² --> TRL7. Spray pyrolysis technique optimized producing GDE of 25 cm² with different configurations • New-design ERCO2 process to produce formic acid/formate TRL4-5. A CO₂ electrolyser towards formic acid has been demonstrated at a laboratory scale at flow rates of 0.2 L CO₂ · min⁻¹ (10 cm²).--> TRL7. CO₂ electrolyser (20 L CO₂ · min⁻¹ ;1,000 cm²) operated at a cement plant to abate real emissions, yielding formic acid in a continuous mode.
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (nature of the innovations)

4.3.2 ENVIRONMENTAL KPIS

4.3.2.1 D3_ENV_01: PERCENTAGE CHANGE OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_ENV_01
Indicator name	Percentage change in environmental impact
Formula	$100 * ((\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq before} - \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq after}) / \text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq before})$
Unit	%

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_ENV_01
Description	This indicator measures the reduction in CO ₂ eq. emissions (measured in kilograms of CO ₂ equivalent, kg CO ₂ eq) as a result of implementing the DEMO solutions. The indicator is expressed as a percentage, reflecting the efficiency of these solutions in reducing CO ₂ emissions compared to a conventional scenario where these solutions were not applied.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 3 partners
Timeframe	- Estimation of CO ₂ eq from conventional routes [M35] - Estimation of CO ₂ eq from innovative routes [M35, M45]
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Kapetaki & Barbosa (2018) [11]

4.3.2.2 D3_ENV_02: GLOBAL WARMING POTENTIAL (GWP)

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_ENV_02
Indicator name	Global Warming Potential (GWP)
Formula	GWP will be calculated based on separate indicators i.e. Climate Change Biogenic, Climate Change Fossil, Climate Change Land Use, and Land Use Change.
Unit	kg CO ₂ -equivalents (kg CO ₂ -eq) per functional unit (FU)
Description	Quantifies the contribution to global warming of a unit of greenhouse gas emitted, usually measured in CO ₂ -equivalents.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 3 partners
Timeframe	- Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Ramirez et al. (2020) [12]

4.3.3 ECONOMIC KPIS

4.3.3.1 D3_ECON_01: LEVELISED COST OF FORMIC ACID

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_ECON_01
Indicator name	Levelised Cost of formic acid

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER		D3_ECON_01
Formula	$\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (CAPEX_t + OPEX_t) \cdot \frac{1}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAPEX_t: Capital costs i.e. costs associated with the initial investment and capital expenditures in year t. • OPEX_t: Operating and maintenance Costs i.e. ongoing costs required for operation and maintenance of the formic acid production demonstrator in year t. • E_t: Amount of formic acid produced i.e. quantity of formic acid produced in year t. • r: Discount Rate i.e. the rate used to discount future costs and revenues to their present value. It reflects the time value of money. • n: Lifetime of the project i.e. the total duration (in years) over which the formic acid production project is expected to operate. 	
Unit	€/ kg formic acid	
Description	The levelised Cost of formic acid is a measure used to compare the cost-effectiveness of formic acid production methods over their entire lifecycle. It is calculated as the total cost of producing formic acid, including capital, operating, and maintenance costs, divided by the total amount of formic acid produced over the system's lifetime.	
Responsible partner	GCPV & APRIA	
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]	
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T5.5]	
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase	
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners	

4.3.3.2 D3_ECON_02: LEVELISED COST OF CO₂ CAPTURE

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER		D3_ECON_02
Indicator name	Levelised Cost of CO ₂ Capture	
Formula	$\frac{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{CAPEX_{CO_2,t} + OPEX_{CO_2,t}}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{M_t}{(1+r)^t}}$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAPEX CO_{2,t}: Capital costs specifically for CO₂ capture in year t. • OPEX CO_{2,t}: Operating and maintenance costs specifically for CO₂ capture in year t. • M_t: Mass of CO₂ captured in year t. 	

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_ECON_02
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • r: Discount Rate i.e. the rate used to discount future costs and revenues to their present value. It reflects the time value of money. • n: Lifetime of the project i.e. the total duration (in years) over which the bio-oil production project is expected to operate.
Unit	€/ kg CO ₂ captured
Description	The levelised Cost of CO ₂ Capture is an economic indicator used to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of CO ₂ capture technologies. It is calculated by dividing the total cost of capturing CO ₂ (including capital, operational, and maintenance costs) by the total amount of CO ₂ captured over the system's lifetime.
Responsible partner	SINTEF & GCPV
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T5.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.3.3.3 D3_ECON_03: POTENTIAL RETURN ON INVESTMENT

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_ECON_03
Indicator name	Potential Return on Investment (ROI) Net profit/total investment * 100%
Formula	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Net Profit: The total revenue generated by the investment minus the total costs (both capital and operational costs). • Total Investment: The total capital expenditure (CAPEX) invested in the project.
Unit	%
Description	ROI is a measure of profitability expressed as a percentage, indicating how effectively the investment is generating profit relative to its cost.
Responsible partner	GCPV & APRIA
Timeframe	- Estimation [M39, M48]
Means of verification	Techno-economic task [T6.5]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.3.4 SOCIAL KPIS

4.3.4.1 D3_SOC_01: HOURS OF WORK PER AMOUNT OF CO₂ CAPTURED

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_SOC_01
Indicator name	Hours of work per amount of CO ₂ captured
Formula	Number of new hours/t CO ₂
Unit	h/ t CO ₂
Description	This indicator measures the time dedicated to capture 1 t of CO ₂
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T5.5 [M32] - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	Proposed by DEMO partners

4.3.4.2 D3_SOC_02: JOBS CREATION

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_SOC_02
Indicator name	Direct/indirect jobs creation due to project implementation
Formula	Number of new jobs/years
Unit	Number/y
Description	This indicator measures the total number of jobs created as a direct or indirect result of the implementation of CAPTUS project.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 3 partners
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of WP5 - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	4
Source of inspiration	- CAPTUS GA [6] - BioSFerA project [7] - FUELPHORIA project [5]

4.3.4.3 D3_SOC_03: HEALTH AND SAFETY OF EMPLOYEES

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D3_SOC_03
Indicator name	Health and Safety of employees
Formula	-
Unit	Number of incidents
Description	This indicator tracks the number of health and safety incidents or accidents that occur in relation to the DEMO 3 implementation and operation.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 3 partners
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of WP5 - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]
Target (success indicator)	0
Source of inspiration	- GA - BioSFerA - FUELPHORIA

5 CAPTUS SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS PER DEMONSTRATOR

5.1 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 1 (D1)

For D1, 13 supplemental indicators were selected: 2 technical, 7 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social. A summary table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target (success indicator), and Source of inspiration. The completed template is provided in Annex II.

5.1.1 TECHNICAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D1_TECH_S_01	D1_TECH_S_02
Indicator name	Production of acetate	Production of TAGs
Formula	Production of acetate	Amount of TAGs produced
Unit	kg/day and kg/y	kg/day and kg/y
Description	This is a supplementary indicator. This indicator is related to Stage 2 and, in particular, the amount of acetate produced per day and per year. Moreover, it relates to D1_TECH_02.	This is a supplementary indicator. This indicator is related to Stage 3 and, in particular, the amount of TAGs produced per day and per year. Moreover, it relates to D1_TECH_04.
Responsible partner	BBEPP	
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Monthly measurements - Measurement at the end of the project [M48] 	
Means of verification	Measurement of the mass of the end-product [Task 3.5]	
Target (success indicator)	1.7 kg/d during CAPTUS	360 g TAG/d (>180 g/d after DSP) during CAPTUS
Source of inspiration	CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6] - FUELPHORIA project [5]

5.1.2 ENVIRONMENTAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

INDICATOR IDENTIFIER	D1_ENV_S_01	D1_ENV_S_02	D1_ENV_S_03	D1_ENV_S_04	D1_ENV_S_05	D1_ENV_S_06	D1_ENV_S_07
Indicator name	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Human Toxicity Potential (HTP)	Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity (FAETP)	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (TETP)	Photochemical Ozone Formation Potential (POFP)	Acidification Potential (AP)	Eutrophication Potential (EP)
Formula	According to LCA4CCU project, the use of CML (Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden) impact categories are recommended, as it harmonizes with the International Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) System.						
Unit	kg CFC-11-equivalents (kg CFC-11-eq) per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg ethene-equivalents (kg C2H4-eq) per FU	kg SO ₂ -equivalents (kg SO ₂ -eq) per FU	kg phosphate-equivalents (kg PO ₄ -eq) per FU
Description	Measures the potential damage to the ozone layer caused by emissions of ozone-depleting substances.	Quantifies the potential human health impacts resulting from exposure to toxic substances, considering factors such as toxicity and persistence.	Assesses the potential impact on freshwater aquatic ecosystems due to the release of toxic substances.	Measures the potential impact on terrestrial ecosystems due to the release of toxic substances.	Quantifies the potential to form ground-level ozone, which contributes to smog formation.	Measures the potential to contribute to acidification of ecosystems, primarily through emissions of acidifying substances.	Quantifies the potential for nutrient enrichment of ecosystems, leading to harmful algal blooms and other ecological impacts.
Responsible partner	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 1 partners						
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]						
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]						
Target	To be defined at a later phase						
Source of inspiration	Ramirez et al. (2020) [12]						

5.1.3 ECONOMIC SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D1_ECON_S_01	D1_ECON_S_02
Indicator name	Specific Capital Costs	Specific Operational Costs
Formula	Total CAPEX/ Total quantity of TAGs produced	Total OPEX/ Total quantity of TAGs produced
Unit	€/TAGs kg	€/TAGs kg
Description	Represents the initial investment expenses required to establish the new process for TAGs from CO ₂ in the two-step fermentation process, normalized per unit of production capacity.	Represents all expenditures associated with the daily operation of the DEMO for TAGs from CO ₂ in the two-step fermentation process, expressed per unit of production.
Responsible	UNIGE & DRAXIS (help from ARC & BBEPP)	
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]	
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T3.5]	
Target	To be defined at a later phase	
Inspiration	CO2SMOS project [8], BioSFerA project [7], FUELPHORIA project [5]	

5.1.4 SOCIAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D1_SOC_S_01	D1_SOC_S_02
Indicator name	Health and Safety of employees	Gender equity of employees
Unit	Number of incidents	Number of female employees hired per year.
Description	This indicator tracks the number of health and safety incidents or accidents that occur in relation to the DEMO 1 implementation and operation.	This indicator measures the number of female employees, reflecting the commitment to gender equity within personnel involved in DEMO1 activities.
Responsible	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 1 partners	
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T3.5 [M32] - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]	
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]	
Target	Zero incidents	50%
Inspiration	CAPTUS GA [6], BioSFerA project [7], FUELPHORIA project [5]	

5.2 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 2 (D2)

For D2, 17 supplemental indicators were selected: 5 technical, 7 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social. A summary table is provided per category including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target and Source of inspiration. The completed template is provided in Annex III.

5.2.1 TECHNICAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D2_TECH_S_01	D2_TECH_S_02	D2_TECH_S_03	D2_TECH_S_04	D2_TECH_S_05
Indicator name	Concentration of conditioned CO ₂	Microalgae growth rate	HTL energy conversion efficiency	Amount of produced Bio-oils	Bio-oil yield
Formula	No formula, direct measurement	Final biomass concentration - Initial biomass concentration / cultivation time	Energy content of bio-oil / energy content of input biomass x 100%	Total bio-oil produced by HTL during the demonstration period	Mass of bio-oil produced / mass of biomass feedstock x 100%
Unit	%	g/L/day or g/m ² /day	%	kg/y	%
Description	CO ₂ concentration in the outlet of the capture system (or in the inlet of the PBRs for microalgae production)	Microalgae growth rate indicates the rate at which microalgae biomass increases in the photobioreactor over a given period.	HTL conversion efficiency measures the efficiency of converting biomass into bio-oil through the HTL process. It compares the energy content of the produced bio-oil to the energy content of the input biomass.	Amount of bio-oil produced per year	Bio-oil yield quantifies the amount of bio-oil produced from a given amount of biomass during the HTL process. It is expressed as a percentage of the mass of bio-oil relative to the mass of the biomass.
Responsible partner	NOVIS supported by A4F	A4F	CIRCE supported by CERTH, A4F	CIRCE supported by CERTH, A4F	CIRCE supported by CERTH, A4F
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32], - Measurement at the end of the project [M48]				
Means of verification	CO ₂ concentration measurement in the outlet of NOVIS system [Task 4.5]	Measurement of biomass concentration and/or surface [Task 4.5]	Measurement of the energy content of bio-oil and of biomass [Task 4.5]	Measurement of bio-oil captured per year [Task 4.3, Task 4.4]	Measurement of the mass of bio-oil and of algae biomass [Task 4.3, Task 4.4]
Target	To be defined at a later phase	(72 m ²): → during CAPTUS: 175-190 kg/y	To be defined at a later phase	80 kg/y	To be defined at a later phase
Source of inspiration	- CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6] - BioSFerA project [7]	- FUELPHORIA project [5]	-	- CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) [6]	-

5.2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

INDICATOR	D2_ENV_S_01	D2_ENV_S_02	D2_ENV_S_03	D2_ENV_S_04	D2_ENV_S_05	D2_ENV_S_06	D2_ENV_S_07
Indicator name	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Human Toxicity Potential (HTP)	Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity (FAETP)	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (TETP)	Photochemical Ozone Formation Potential (POFP)	Acidification Potential (AP)	Eutrophication Potential (EP)
Formula	According to LCA4CCU project, the use of CML (Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden) impact categories are recommended, as it harmonizes with the International Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) System.						
Unit	kg CFC-11-equivalents (kg CFC-11-eq) per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg ethene-equivalents (kg C2H4-eq) per FU	kg SO2-equivalents (kg SO2-eq) per FU	kg phosphate-equivalents (kg PO4-eq) per FU
Description	Measures the potential damage to the ozone layer caused by emissions of ozone-depleting substances.	Quantifies the potential human health impacts from exposure to toxic substances, considering factors such as toxicity and persistence.	Assesses the potential impact on freshwater aquatic ecosystems due to the release of toxic substances.	Measures the potential impact on terrestrial ecosystems due to the release of toxic substances.	Quantifies the potential to form ground-level ozone, which contributes to smog formation.	Measures the potential to contribute to acidification of ecosystems, primarily through emissions of acidifying substances.	Quantifies the potential for nutrient enrichment of ecosystems, leading to harmful algal blooms and other ecological impacts.
Responsible	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners						
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]						
Means of verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]						
Target	To be defined at a later phase						
Inspiration	Ramirez et al. (2020) [12]						

5.2.3 ECONOMIC SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D2_ECON_S_01	D2_ECON_S_02
Indicator name	Specific Capital Costs	Specific Operational Costs
Formula	Total CAPEX/ Total quantity of bio-oils produced	Total OPEX/ Total quantity of bio-oils produced
Unit	€/ kg bio-oils	€/ kg bio-oils
Description	Represents the initial investment expenses required to establish the new process for producing bio-oils from CO ₂ in the two-step fermentation process, normalized per unit of production capacity.	Represents all expenditures associated with the daily operation of the DEMO for producing bio-oils from CO ₂ in the two-step fermentation process, expressed per unit of production.
Responsible	UNIGE & DRAXIS (help from ARC & BBEP)	
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]	
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T4.5]	
Target	To be defined at a later phase	
Inspiration	CO2SMOS project [8], BioSFerA project [7], FUELPHORIA project [5]	

5.2.4 SOCIAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D2_SOC_S_01	D2_SOC_S_02
Indicator name	Health and Safety of employees	Gender equity of employees
Unit	Number of incidents	Number of female employees hired per year.
Description	This indicator tracks the number of health and safety incidents in relation to the DEMO 2 operation.	This indicator measures the number of female employees, within personnel involved in DEMO 2 activities.
Responsible	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners	
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32] - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]	
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]	
Target	Zero incidents	50%
Inspiration	CAPTUS GA [6], BioSFerA project [7], FUELPHORIA project [5]	

5.3 CAPTUS DEMONSTRATION SITE 3 (D3)

For D3, 15 supplemental indicators were selected: 3 technical, 8 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social. A summary table is provided per category including the following: Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target and Source of inspiration. The completed template is provided in Annex IV.

5.3.1 TECHNICAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D3_TECH_S_01	D3_TECH_S_02	D3_TECH_S_03
Indicator name	CO ₂ capture rate	CO ₂ purity	Sorbent degradation rate
Formula	CO ₂ flow in (kg/day) - CO ₂ flow out (kg/day)	CO ₂ flow out of desorber (mol/s) / total flow of non-condensable gases out of the desorber (mol/s)	Change in working capacity (mol/kg) / Sorbent working capacity (mol/kg) at the start of the campaign * 100 % / campaign duration (days)
Unit	kg/day	%	%/day
Description	The rate at which CO ₂ is captured using CSAR	CO ₂ concentration on a dry basis at the outlet of the capture system (or in the inlet of the CO ₂ electrolyser for formic acids production)	The rate at which the relative sorbent working capacity decreases over the entire campaign, if the operating conditions (reactor temperatures, desorber pressure, sorbent circulation rate) are maintained constant
Responsible	SINTEF & GCPV	SINTEF & GCPV	SINTEF & GCPV
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T5.5 [M32] - Continuous measurements to calculate the average rate of CO ₂ captured [M32-M48].	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T5.5 [M32] - Continuous measurements during demonstration	- Estimate at the end of the project [M48]
Means of verification	Measurements of CO ₂ in flue gas after the CSAR reactor compared to the measured CO ₂ fraction in the GCPV flue gas and the flow rate through the reactor [Task 5.5]	Estimated based on the CO ₂ capture rate from the adsorber and the humidity measurement on the desorber outlet [Task 5.5]	Monitoring of the sorbent working capacity at a chosen operating condition during the campaign [T 5.5]
Target	57 kg/day, → during CAPTUS ca. 2.4 tons CO ₂	75%	< 1% per day
Source of inspiration	- CAPTUS GA (demo-site-specific characteristics and needs) - Feasible capture capacity demonstrated by CSAR	- Results from UNICAN show that similar performance is achieved with CO ₂ purities in the range of 75-100 % - Due to technical issues with steam addition, a CO ₂ purity of 50-60% is currently achieved by CSAR, which is significantly below the design purity of > 90%. While ongoing efforts will attempt to overcome the technical issues with steam addition, with other ongoing optimization efforts a purity of 75% would be achievable even without steam.	Reasonable estimate based on a recent demonstration at a waste-to-energy plant that would allow 1000 hours of operation, while replacing the sorbent a maximum of 1 time.

5.3.2 ENVIRONMENTAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

INDICATOR	D3_ENV_S_01	D3_ENV_S_02	D3_ENV_S_03	D3_ENV_S_04	D3_ENV_S_05	D3_ENV_S_06	D3_ENV_S_07	D3_ENV_S_08
Indicator name	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	Human Toxicity Potential (HTP)	Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (TETP)	Photochemical Ozone Formation Potential	Acidification Potential (AP)	Eutrophication Potential (EP)	Use of renewable electricity surplus
Formula	According to LCA4CCU project, the use of CML (Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden) impact categories are recommended, as it harmonizes with the International Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) System.							-
Unit	kg CFC-11-equivalents (kg CFC-11-eq) per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg 1,4-DB-eq or similar toxic equivalents per FU	kg ethene-equivalents (kg C2H4-eq) per FU	kg SO2-equivalents (kg SO2-eq) per FU	kg phosphate-equivalents (kg PO4-eq) per FU	% of energy needed for CO ₂ capture (OR total energy needed for demo) that comes from RE surplus
Description	Measures the potential damage to the ozone layer caused by emissions of ozone-depleting substances.	Quantifies the potential human health impacts from exposure to toxic substances	Assesses the potential impact on freshwater aquatic ecosystems due to the release of toxic substances.	Measures the potential impact on terrestrial ecosystems due to the release of toxic substances.	Quantifies the potential to form ground-level ozone, which contributes to smog formation.	Measures the potential to contribute to acidification of ecosystems, primarily through emissions of acidifying substances.	Quantifies the potential for nutrient enrichment of ecosystems, leading to harmful algal blooms and other impacts.	How much of the extra energy needed (either for CO ₂ capture or considering the global process) comes from RE surplus.
Responsible	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 2 partners							
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]							
Verification	LCA of the entire value chain [T6.4]							GCPV & APRIA
Target	To be defined at a later phase							20 kW, → during CAPTUS ca. 175 MWh/year
Inspiration	Ramirez et al. (2020) [12]							CAPTUS GA

5.3.3 ECONOMIC SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D3_ECON_S_01	D3_ECON_S_02
Indicator name	Specific Capital Costs	Specific Operational Costs
Formula	Total CAPEX/ Total quantity of formic acid produced	Total OPEX/ Total quantity of formic acid produced
Unit	€/ kg formic acid	€/ kg formic acid
Description	It represents the initial investment costs required for setting up the CO ₂ capture, CSAR, and GDEs for upscaled CO ₂ electroreduction reactors. This indicator is expressed in euros per unit of production capacity.	It represents all expenses associated with the day-to-day operations of the CO ₂ capture, CSAR, and GDEs for upscaled CO ₂ electroreduction. This includes costs for labor, maintenance, electricity, and consumables. This indicator is expressed in euros per unit of formic acid produced.
Responsible	GCPV & APRIA	
Timeframe	Estimation [M39, M48]	
Means of verification	Techno-economic task and LCC [T6.5, T6.4] DEMO operation task [T5.5]	
Target	To be defined at a later phase	
Inspiration	CO2SMOS project [8], BioSFerA project [7], FUELPHORIA project [5]	

5.3.4 SOCIAL SUPPLEMENTAL INDICATORS

IDENTIFIER	D3_SOC_S_01	D4_SOC_S_02
Indicator name	Gender equity of employees	Employee skills and training in innovative processing
Unit	Number of female employees hired per year.	Number of training hours dedicated to innovative processing / year
Description	This indicator measures the number of female employees, reflecting the commitment to gender equity within personnel involved in DEMO 3 activities.	This indicator measures the total number of training hours allocated specifically to enhancing skills in innovative processing techniques that will be developed in project annually.
Responsible	DRAXIS supported by DEMO 3 partners	
Timeframe	- Initial measurement at the beginning of T4.5 [M32] - Measurement every 4 months until the end of the project [M48]	
Means of verification	s-LCA [T6.4]	
Target	50%	To be defined at a later phase
Inspiration	CAPTUS GA [6], BioSFerA project [7], FUELPHORIA project [5]	

6 KPIs EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

As already mentioned in Section 3.1, the KPIs are designed to measure and monitor the performance of each demonstration site independently, without focusing on implementing direct comparisons between sites. This approach is based on the specific information provided by each DEMO-involved partner, ensuring that the results are context-specific and not intended for cross-site comparison.

The selection of KPIs has been analysed and a list of KPIs is presented for each demonstration site in Chapter 4 i.e. Section 4.1 for D1, Section 4.2 for D2, and Section 4.3 for D3. Analysis per category (KPI categories: Technical, Environmental, Economic, and Social) is provided in the relevant sub-sections of Chapter 4 sections for each demonstrator. For each KPI, a table is provided per category (technical, environmental, economic, social) including the following: *Indicator name, Formula, Unit, Description, Responsible partner, Timeframe, Means of verification, Target (success indicator), and Source of inspiration.*

This chapter presents the *methodology for evaluating the Key Performance Indicators* within the context of the CAPTUS project given the fact that there is not a separate task dedicated to the monitoring of the progress towards the KPIs. Considering this, the evaluation process will be coordinated by specific project teams, each responsible for different KPI categories.

For *Technical KPIs*, each technical WP leader will coordinate the collection of calculated KPIs and record the progress against those KPIs which will be provided in periodic reports No 2, No3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48]. To be more specific:

- WP3 Leader (BBEPP): Responsible for coordinating and recording the progress of D1 technical KPIs.
- WP4 Leader (A4F): Responsible for coordinating and recording the progress of D2 technical KPIs.
- WP5 Leader (UNICAN): Responsible for coordinating and recording the progress of D3 technical KPIs.

It should be clarified that the responsible partner for data collection, timing, and calculation formulas for each specific technical KPI has already been defined in the technical KPIs tables and consolidated Excel files. Each WP leader is solely responsible for the coordination and reporting purposes, not for the actual calculation of the technical KPIs unless this is stated in the KPIs table.

For *Environmental, Economic and Social KPIs*, DRAXIS will coordinate the collection of calculated environmental, economic, and social KPIs and record the progress against those KPIs under the activity of T6.4 & T6.5. The progress will be provided in periodic reports No 2, No 3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48]. As mentioned above, the responsible partner for data collection, timing, and calculation formulas for each specific KPI has already been defined in the KPIs tables and consolidated Excel files. DRAXIS's role is solely for coordination and reporting purposes of environmental, economic, and social not for the actual calculation of the KPIs, unless this is stated in the KPIs table.

The figure below outlines the key points of the evaluation methodology. Monitoring of the main KPIs (see Chapter 4) is obligatory, while supplemental KPIs (see Chapter 5) are not; however, we strongly recommend applying the same approach to them for all demonstrators and category types.

Technical KPIs

Measurement by responsible partners as indicated in Excel
Coordinate the task of evaluation by technical WP leaders i.e. WP3 (BBEPP), WP4 (A4F), WP5 (UNICAN)
Progress against those KPIs will be provided in periodic reports No 2, No3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48] by technical WP leaders

Environmental KPIs

Measurement by responsible partners as indicated in Excel
Coordinate the task of evaluation by DRAXIS
Progress against those KPIs will be provided in periodic reports No 2, No3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48] by DRAXIS after validation with technical WP leaders

Economic KPIs

Measurement by responsible partners as indicated in Excel
Coordinate the task of evaluation by DRAXIS
Progress against those KPIs will be provided in periodic reports No 2, No3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48] by DRAXIS after validation with technical WP leaders

Social KPIs

Measurement by responsible partners as indicated in Excel
Coordinate the task of evaluation by DRAXIS
Progress against those KPIs will be provided in periodic reports No 2, No3 [RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48] by DRAXIS after validation with technical WP leaders

Figure 11: Key points of the KPIs evaluation methodology

7 CONCLUSION - NEXT STEPS

Deliverable 2.3 has successfully established a framework for assessing the performance of the CAPTUS project's demonstrators. This methodology is built upon a set of indicators, including 40 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and 45 supplemental indicators, tailored to each of the three demonstration sites (D1, D2, D3). These indicators cover technical, environmental, economic, and social dimensions, ensuring a holistic evaluation of the project's impact.

In particular,

For Demonstrator D1 (Steel Plant):

- ✓ 14 KPIs were selected: 7 technical, 3 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social;
- ✓ 13 supplemental indicators were selected: 2 technical, 7 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social.

For Demonstrator D2 (Chemical Plant):

- ✓ 14 KPIs were selected: 6 technical, 3 environmental, 3 economic, and 2 social;
- ✓ 17 supplemental indicators were selected: 5 technical, 7 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social.

For Demonstrator D3 (Cement Plant):

- ✓ 12 KPIs were selected: 5 technical, 2 environmental, 3 economic, and 3 social;
- ✓ 15 supplemental indicators were selected: 3 technical, 8 environmental, 2 economic, and 2 social.

Additionally, the deliverable outlines clear responsibilities for coordinating the collection and reporting of KPIs which is essential for the successful implementation and monitoring of the project's performance metrics.

Next Steps

Moving forward, the focus will be on implementing the evaluation methodology and continuously monitoring the KPIs to assess the CAPTUS solutions' impact by the responsible partners. Technical WP leaders and DRAXIS are assigned specific roles to ensure comprehensive and accurate reporting. The *KPIs* to be tracked mandatory include:

For Demonstrator D1 (Steel Plant):

- ✓ Technical: CO₂ captured, Energy efficiency of the overall process, Acetate productivity, Acetate concentration of 1st fermentation stage, TAGs productivity, TAGs concentration of 2nd fermentation stage, Technology Readiness Level.
- ✓ Environmental: Percentage change of environmental impact, Global Warming Potential (GWP), Use of renewable electricity surplus.
- ✓ Economic: Levelised Cost of TAGs, Potential Return on Investment.
- ✓ Social: Jobs creation, Employees' skills and training.

For Demonstrator D2 (Chemical Plant):

- ✓ Technical: CO₂ captured, Energy efficiency of the overall process, Energy efficiency of CO₂ capture, Bio-oil mass conversion efficiency from CO₂, Bio-oil energy conversion efficiency from CO₂, Technology Readiness Level.
- ✓ Environmental: Percentage change of environmental impact, Global Warming Potential (GWP), Use of renewable electricity surplus.
- ✓ Economic: Levelised Cost of bio-oil, Levelised Cost of CO₂ Capture, Potential Return on Investment.
- ✓ Social: Jobs creation, Employees' skills and training.

For Demonstrator D3 (Cement Plant):

- ✓ Technical: CO₂ captured, Energy efficiency of CO₂ conversion, Formic acid mass conversion efficiency from CO₂, Technology Readiness Level.
- ✓ Environmental: Percentage change of environmental impact, Global Warming Potential (GWP).
- ✓ Economic: Levelised Cost of formic acid, Levelised Cost of CO₂ Capture, Potential Return on Investment.
- ✓ Social: Hours of work per amount of CO₂ captured, Jobs creation, Health and Safety of employees.

The insights gained from this evaluation will not only inform the ongoing development of CAPTUS technologies but also provide valuable contributions to the broader field of carbon capture and utilization technologies. The iterative assessment process will enable continuous improvement, ensuring that the CAPTUS solutions are optimized for maximum sustainability and impact. Regular reporting on KPI target achievement in the project's upcoming periodic reports (RP2: M17 – M32, RP3: M33 – M48) will be crucial for tracking progress and making necessary adjustments.

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